

The Influence of Workarounds On Cross-Organisational Data Sharing In Highly Regulated Industries

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ABSTRACT

While using and sharing data is becoming more important, there is an increasing amount of privacy regulations being introduced. Existing literature shows that privacy regulations decrease the flexibility in information systems and the ease of data sharing. Within organisations, workarounds arise to bypass privacy regulations. In this research, the focus is on workarounds while sharing data between organisations in highly regulated industries. These research results can help recognize processes' flaws, where workarounds originate from. Data was brought in through three interviews, each taking place in a different industry, those were conducted with data processors. Since the introduction of strict privacy regulations, the perceived risk of workarounds increased, resulting in strict processes and non-tolerance information systems. Structural workarounds were not found in this study, only incidental workarounds. Even though the amount of data being shared between organisations is increasing, privacy regulations have a negative impact on quantity of data sharing.

Keywords: *Digital Privacy, Data Sharing, Cross-Organisational, Workarounds, Privacy Regulations.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's economy, data is becoming increasingly important. The influence of digital platforms is increasing the use of digital products and services. Sharing data is becoming increasingly crucial and valuable in organisations. According to Hulsens (2020), data sharing allows chains to work more efficiently and could save participating parties money. But with all these upsides organisations cannot just start data sharing. Privacy regulations such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) have been constructed to help better protect the right to privacy. But these regulations have

prompted many organisations to expand their privacy policy regulations (Ian Lloyd, 2017). Although privacy regulations protect privacy, they can make it more difficult for organisations to share data. Some organisations may be fully compliant with privacy regulations however workarounds could still occur. So this paper focuses on workarounds for sharing data in highly regulated industries. The authors questioned whether there are workarounds between organisations regarding data sharing. What are the factors that influence the perceived risk and expected gain to share data and create workarounds? What is the biggest bottleneck regarding the regulations? This paper aims to deliver knowledge about workarounds between organisations and their influence on the amount of data being shared. Furthermore, this paper will deliver academic knowledge about the behaviour of workers in highly regulated industries regarding data sharing and privacy regulations. This knowledge could also be beneficial for these highly regulated industries because often workarounds are created to mitigate flaws in processes. Hereby organisations can better locate flaws and adjust their processes.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the context of this research, highly regulated industries will be discussed. This paper will refer to highly regulated industries as the industries where privacy regulations are the most strict like: healthcare, finance, education, and government. Because workarounds could vary in different types, this paper will provide a promising research direction to understand the impact of workarounds on the negative relationship between privacy regulations and the quantity of data being shared. Some examples of workarounds could be sharing screenshots of sensitive data via email in conflict with company policy or using spreadsheets instead of the standard information systems because of the spreadsheet's flexibility.

Following these workarounds, the current

literature such as Röder, et al. (2014), Tucker & Edmondson (2003), Stutzer & Rushton (2015) and Alter (2014) mainly focuses on the meaning and theories of workarounds and not on implementing these theories to specific relations. Therefore, this paper will use the theory of workarounds by Alter (2014) to address the relationship between privacy regulations and data sharing. Furthermore, the current research about workarounds only focuses on workarounds within organisations, this paper will fill in that gap by focusing on workarounds between two separate organisations with distinct information systems. An example of this could be a government agency sharing information with an insurer.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To analyse the influence of workarounds on privacy regulations regarding data sharing between organisations in highly regulated industries the following research question and sub question have been formulated: *“In what way do workarounds influence the relationship between data privacy regulations and data sharing between organisations in highly regulated industries?”*

Sub research question: *“Have workarounds arisen in the process regarding data sharing between organisations?”*

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Cross-organisational Data Sharing

In the existing literature, there are a few important success factors that facilitate data sharing between organisations. These can be split up into two different categories: technological and organisational. On the technological side, it is important that the information systems used by the different parties are interoperable and can facilitate the effective sharing of data (Yang & Maxwell, 2011). This often requires close collaboration, which is why organisational factors also play a role.

One of the most important organisational factors is trust (Pardo & Tayi, 2007; Chen et al., 2014). This factor is arguably more important than the technological factor. This is demonstrated in the research of Eden et al. (2016) where they found that, despite having the technological capability, organisations are often still too cautious to share data with other organisations due to the fear of data breaches.

Impact of Privacy Regulation On Cross-Organisational Data Sharing

Although many different privacy regulations across the globe affect organisations differently depending on the region that they operate in, these regulations all cause the need for extra precautions

regarding the sharing and storing of data.

When looking at the effect of privacy regulations on data sharing it can be argued that there is a negative effect of these regulations on the amount and quality of data that is and can be shared. If no regulations were in place, information sharing would be possible through all means. whereas now organisations have to adhere to extra rules to ensure the privacy of personal information. These extra steps in the process can act as a barrier to the sharing of data.

An example of this can be found in scientific research which uses data from clinical studies, the problem has arisen that consent forms in different countries with varying regulations have different required language. This makes it very difficult to share data across borders. The required language can also change over time which makes it difficult to get access to older research data due to changed privacy regulations (White et al., 2022). Furthermore, privacy regulation also has been found to have an impact on the costs of implementation of robust information systems capable of sharing and storing information in compliance with the regulations (Adjerid et al., 2016).

Finally, the need for privacy measures in information systems could increase the complexity of these systems and can cause a negative effect on the ease of use. According to the technology acceptance model this can in turn cause a lower rate of adoption of these systems (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008). This however has not yet been archived in current literature.

Workarounds

According to Alter (2014) a workaround is “a goal-driven adaptation, improvisation, or other change to one or more aspects of an existing work system in order to overcome, bypass, or minimise the impact of obstacles, exceptions, anomalies, mishaps, established practices, management expectations, or structural constraints that are perceived as preventing that work system or its participants from achieving the desired level of efficiency, effectiveness, or other organisational or personal goals”. Workarounds are conceptualised as the degree of departure from an intended change design due to employees dynamically shaping innovations as they diffuse into an organisation (Barrett & Stephens, 2016).

Much of the research is focused on how employees break data protocol (Stutzer & Rushton, 2015) and use the systems in ways that are in conflict with policy or regulations (Menachemi & Collum, 2011). These behaviours are often labelled “workarounds”.

Privacy regulations could directly, or indirectly through an increased complex information system, be the cause for a workaround to occur. Study has shown a pattern in the creation of such workarounds

within organisations: 1) sharing knowledge about workarounds 2) consensus building 3) co-design workarounds 4) formalise workarounds and lastly, 5) continuous usage of workarounds. Röder et. al. (2014) states various factors which could negatively or positively affect the toleration of workarounds. Examples that negatively influence toleration of workarounds are legal consequences, deviations in revenue, and life-critical treatment. On the other hand, factors that positively influence the toleration of workarounds are increased process quality, shortcuts, work life balance, improved throughput time, and process clarification. These are respectively categorised as perceived risk and expected gain. Röder et. al. (2014) concludes that information systems play a significant role in this setting, as they standardise routines and increase accountability, this indicates that an organisation prevents workarounds from happening, given the perceived risk. This research will focus on cross-organisational data sharing, which might differ from the current findings on perceived risk and gain, which is focused on intra-organisational data sharing.

Conceptual Model

To identify the relationship between workarounds and the negative influence of privacy regulations on cross-organisational data sharing a conceptual model is created as represented in *figure 1*. In this conceptual model, cross-organisational data sharing is the dependent variable, privacy regulation is the independent variable and workarounds are the moderating variable. This moderating variable “workarounds” is derived from the existing theory of workarounds by Alter (2014) and Röder et al. (2014). Whether workarounds arise in a certain process is dependent on two main variables, these are perceived risk and expected gain. Expected gain increases the likelihood of a workaround arising, and perceived risk decreases the likelihood of a workaround arising (Röder et al., 2014). As stated in the knowledge gap, it cannot be concluded from existing literature that workarounds do indeed arise in the processes related to cross-organisational data sharing. This is represented in this research by the sub question: “*Have workarounds arisen in the process regarding data sharing between organisations?*”. This question aims to confirm the existence of workarounds in cross-organisational data sharing.

The conceptual model shows the hypothesised negative relationship of privacy regulation on cross-organisational data sharing which is supported by the first hypothesis:

H1: “*Privacy regulations have a negative effect on the quantity of data shared between organisations.*”

Secondly the influence of workarounds on the negative relationship between privacy regulation

and cross-organisational data sharing is supported by the following hypothesis:

H2: “*Workarounds positively moderate the relationship between privacy regulation and data sharing.*”

Figure 1: Conceptual model

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to identify in what way workarounds influence the relationship between data privacy regulations and data sharing between organisations in highly regulated industries. Based on the theory developed, the research method is explained below.

Methodological Approach

The structure of this study was established through a literature review. Literature was used as the basis for establishing the conceptual model. Different types of theories on workarounds were extracted from the literature. To arrive at the most appropriate literature, a literature review was used. Through this literature review, the different articles are compared on essential aspects. These include how often the article has been cited and whether the article has been peer-reviewed.

To answer the hypotheses that have been formulated, qualitative data will need to be collected, because a comprehensive explanation is needed on the use of workarounds in organisations. As a consequence, the use of quantitative data can be eliminated. Qualitative research is the most appropriate method for arriving at well-generalizable results (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020). The qualitative data obtained in this method will be less controlled but more based on interpretation. As a result, the research will give an in-depth view of data-sharing workarounds between organisations.

The qualitative data used during this research will be primary. This is because the data will have to be taken from different employees in organisations where workarounds are used. Therefore, it can also be concluded that the data will be descriptive (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020).

Data Collection

The qualitative data in this study will be collected through interviews. Through the use of interviews, there will be a better understanding of the subject. Since "workarounds" can be a sensitive

topic to discuss, interviews allow the participant to discuss the issue openly in a private environment. In addition, an interview also provides the participant's honest opinion, which can remain hidden in a focus group.

Several requirements were established for the interview to ensure the validity of this study. Here, it is important to consider companies that process personal data and share data externally. In this regard, the following functions are relevant for conducting the interviews:

- Data Analyst;
- Quality control officer;
- Functional Data Manager;
- Technical Administrator;
- IT Project manager;
- ICT - Advisor;
- Data Privacy Specialist;
- Privacy Security Officer;
- Chief Information Security Officer.

A total of about 40 interviews will be conducted. This allows 10 interviews per industry. Participants will be selected through non-probability sampling. In this case, convenience sampling will be the most approachable choice (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020). Using connections and platforms such as LinkedIn, individuals can be easily approached to participate in the study. Although the interviewee must meet some specific criteria, the research remains accessible.

A minimum of two people will conduct a semi-structured interview. In the interviews, one person will have the task of presenting the specific questions to the interviewed employee, and the other person will support and take minutes. The recording of the interview is an important aspect as they have to be transcribed for analysing results. For this reason, it is important to properly delineate the interview questions so that the answers of different staff members cannot be far apart. This also simplifies the note-taking process.

The semi-structured interviews will be conducted using an interview protocol. Through the established guidelines of the interview protocol, it is ensured that the validity of this study is reinforced. To get the right insights from the interviews, the interview questions are prepared with the use of the defined hypotheses. To ensure that the interview questions were interpreted the same way by the participants, they were checked by multiple practice participants from the network of the researchers.

Privacy Regulations Have A Negative Effect On the Quantity of Data Shared Between Organisations.

Finding out this relationship will require looking at the privacy regulations the company faces and how often data is shared with other companies. In this regard, it is important to examine whether the

interviewee experiences any inconvenience in sharing data due to privacy regulations. It is also essential to ask about certain restrictions or policies that come with data sharing.

Workarounds Positively Moderate the Relationship Between Privacy Regulation And Data Sharing.

Should the interviewee experience hindrance from complying with privacy regulations, workarounds may have arisen in the business processes. Since a workaround is not always noticeable for the interviewee, it is important to inquire whether certain procedures are neglected. This involves asking why these procedures are not followed and if this practice has made data sharing easier. In the case that workarounds occur, it will be necessary to examine whether this will facilitate data sharing with other organisations. It is important to find out if there was a difference to be noticed in sharing data with other organisations before and after the workaround had found its way into the process. Only this will allow concluding whether there is a positive relationship.

Analysis

The results will be analysed through thematic analysis. To ensure that the data is analysed properly, the following three steps are performed. The first step of the analysis is data reduction. It is essential to get a good overview of all the minutes that have been collected from the conducted interviews. After this, the process of selecting, coding, and categorising the data begins. Through coding, answers can be thematised. This helps recognize fixed answers and patterns.

Hereafter, it is important to display the data. A table will be used to provide insight into the various themes that emerged from the data. Hereby, insight is given into the frequency of the themes. This will give insight and clarity about the data and the themes established.

Once the data has been coded and displayed, a revision is essential. A revision ensures that the themes are chosen when coding is a useful and accurate representation of the data. After revision, the data can be determined and used in supporting or rejecting the various hypotheses (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020).

The above three steps should be considered a continuous process. The steps will be repeated and reviewed to strengthen the validity of this study.

Methodological Choices

The research philosophy that will be used is interpretivism philosophy. The reason this philosophy was chosen is because of the in-depth process involved (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020). It is important to discover potential workarounds and assess if they positively affect the relationship between privacy regulations and cross-organisational data sharing. Since workarounds are not talked about freely, it is important to identify them. This is where the interpretivism philosophy fits well. In addition to this, it can therefore also be established that deductive research is used (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020). Based on the hypotheses drawn up, research will be conducted. From this research, several qualitative results will follow and will be analysed. Following the analysis, the hypotheses can be supported or rejected.

RESULTS

Three people with the following functions were interviewed:

- Project manager (data collection);
- Quality control officer;
- ICT - Advisor.

The transcripts of the interviews were coded and divided into five themes that capture the relevant findings from the interviewees (see table 1). The results of this were then used to answer the hypotheses.

Increased Information System Complexity

From the conducted interviews it can be concluded that since the introduction of privacy regulations, in particular the GDPR, Information Systems (IS) have become less flexible and do not allow workarounds by default. The perceived risk of fines and damage to reputation was the main reason for this development. Logging and error messages are deployed to comply with privacy protocols and IS are standardised. Those who determine the success of IS are often the IT department. They are, in addition to logging, responsible for actually monitoring user behaviour. Informal data share requests, which were common in the past, are now made impossible.

Influence of Privacy Regulation

From the conducted interviews it was found that privacy regulations limit the amount of data being shared. Before the privacy regulations organisations would share unsecured emails consisting of Word and Excel sheets containing personal data. But as the organisational awareness of privacy regulations increased, workers started to understand the necessity of sending secured data which heavily decreased the amount of unsecured data sharing. The amount of data sharing was also influenced by the reluctance of customers to share personal data because organisations have to acquire consent from the customer if their data is shared outside of the EU. Lastly, IT systems are more advanced because of privacy regulations, thereby GDPR compliant systems are designed and monitored to prevent possible data leaks.

	Amount of occurrences	Example quote
Increased IS complexity	6	'More secure, more checks better control. So it's not just one or two checks. There's several people on each check.'
Workarounds	3	'We were receiving emails with files with identifiable information from clients'
Influence of privacy regulation	4	'It limits us and the amount of data we share, but we value safety more'
Perceived Risk	7	'It's against the law. So as I said, I think it's at minimum a fine. Probably other consequences as well.'
Perceived Gain	2	'In the past, there were workarounds like asking a non-allowed assistant to view and share data'

Table 1: Summary of results

Perceived Risk & Perceived Gain

From the conducted interviews it can be found that the perceived risk associated with sharing data in a way that is in breach of privacy regulations is notably high. This is related to the severe legal and monetary consequences that organisations and individuals face when the rules and regulations for sharing data safely are not followed. This has spurred organisations to increase awareness among employees, especially if they work with sensitive data. A common theme in the conducted interviews was that, according to the participants, the expected gain never outweighed the perceived risk of sharing data in an unsafe manner that was in conflict with regulations. One participant even outlined an example where highly relevant and useful data was not shared with another organisation due to questions about the receiving organisations' database not being up to their security standards.

Workarounds

Based on the interviews, the following findings can be identified. Firstly, it emerged that organisations use letters to transmit information to other organisations whose clients do not have online communication facilities. As a result, letters containing sensitive information are shared. However, privacy regulations were not the main reason for the creation of this workaround, and thus are less relevant in this research. The data in question cannot be transmitted to the customer in any other way if the customer does not have an email address. Therefore, the data has to be shared by mail. In addition to this, another organisation had to deal with several emails from customers containing sensitive information. Sending such sensitive information in this way fell outside their own policies. However, we cannot speak of a workaround in this part of the process. The fact that the organisation does end up utilising this data, instead of contacting the client asking to do it the formal way, does qualify it as a workaround. This is because the organisation is thereby circumventing its own policies and processing the data in an alternative manner.

Hypotheses

The results of this research are divided into the two different hypotheses.

H1: Privacy Regulations Have A Negative Effect On the Quantity of Data Shared Between Organisations

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the hypothesis can be accepted. With the advent of stricter privacy regulations, organisations have become more rigorous, and different policies have been established to be pursued. Because of those policies, different methods of sharing data became inaccessible and employees are constrained in how they have to share their data. As a result, privacy

regulations have a negative impact on the quantity of data shared between organisations.

H2: Workarounds Positively Moderate the Relationship Between Privacy Regulation And Data Sharing

It can be concluded from the results of the interviews that workarounds are not as common as expected. This is mainly due to the tight enforcement of privacy regulations in organisations. Before the introduction of stricter privacy regulations, this was less of a factor and caused more workarounds. However, when employees lack awareness of the privacy policy and the accompanying penalties, workarounds can still occur. Because there is a lack of awareness, the perceived risk is lower. As a result, the probability of a workaround arising from a lack of awareness regarding privacy policy is higher.

However, it cannot be concluded with any certainty that workarounds positively moderate the relationship between privacy regulation and data sharing.

DISCUSSION

The initial objective of this research was to establish the existence and influence of workarounds in data sharing processes between organisations in highly regulated industries. To analyse these knowledge gaps, three semi-structured interviews were conducted. These interviews had two major findings.

Firstly, this study was able to find examples and accounts of the negative effects of privacy regulations on the amount of data being shared. Secondly, the results of these interviews indicate that while workarounds between organisations can still occur, they occur less frequently since the relevant privacy regulations came into effect.

Furthermore, The examples of workarounds found in the conducted interviews were mostly before or shortly after the introduction of the privacy regulations and were incidental and not structural. This means that workarounds can indeed occur but are less likely to occur in an organised structured manner. The reason for this was found to be the high perceived risk due to the strict consequences of being found in breach of privacy regulations. This means that current privacy regulations have increased the perceived risk to such a degree that it is often difficult for employees to internally justify the creation and continued use of a workaround. This is an important finding because it shows the effect of the strict controls put in place by the relevant privacy regulation.

Due to the incidental nature of these workarounds this research was not able to show a moderating effect on the relationship between privacy regulation and the amount of data sharing.

However, the results of this research constitute

an addition to the current literature on workarounds by extending the scope to include cross-organisational workarounds. This provides a base of knowledge for further research to expand on.

CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the influence of workarounds on the relationship between privacy regulations and data sharing. Sharing data has become increasingly more crucial and valuable in organisations. Data sharing allows organisations to work more efficiently and it could result in monetary gains. Because of privacy regulations, it has become more difficult to share data and due to these privacy regulations workarounds have arisen within organisations. Previous research acknowledged that these workarounds are influenced by the perceived risk and expected gain. Therefore, this paper researched the behaviour of workers in highly regulated industries regarding data sharing and privacy regulations.

It can be established that privacy regulations have a negative impact on the quantity of data being shared between organisations. Organisations have had to develop different policies internally to enforce these regulations. This has reduced the quantity of data sharing. Furthermore, the introduction of stricter privacy regulations has made information systems more complex and as a result has made the data less accessible.

The introduction of privacy regulations was expected to create workarounds in organisations' processes. According to this research, workarounds that are intentionally created are almost non-existent. Organisations have properly covered their policies around privacy regulations and ensure that employees strictly adhere to them. However, incidental workarounds arise through a lack of awareness. This causes the perceived risk to decrease, resulting in a higher chance of a workaround arising. Since no "intentional" workarounds emerged in this study, it cannot be concluded that workarounds have a moderate effect on the relationship between data privacy regulations and data sharing in highly regulated industries.

The results of this study complement the existing literature on workarounds. A practical implication of this research provides clarity on the perceived risk in business processes regarding data sharing. When the employer raises awareness about the potential risk of workarounds in cross-organisational data sharing, it causes the perceived risk among employees to increase, resulting in fewer workarounds emerging.

Due to the limited time and the time an in-depth interview takes, there were too few interviews to be considered a fully representative sample size. This way the research cannot fully answer the research question. These interviews were also conducted online due to the limited time for the

researchers and the interviewees. These online interviews could feel less personal for the interviewee resulting in a less safe environment which could cause the interviewee to be reluctant to share sensitive information.

This research aimed to be generalizable by focusing on highly regulated industries. However, to contribute to the generalisability, the scope could be broader aiming at multiple countries with differing privacy regulations. Our study found that privacy regulations have a negative relationship with the amount of data being shared, but the exact role of workarounds cannot yet be concluded.

The final limitation concerned the possible interviewees from the financial industry. Organisations within the financial industry created strict policies for their workers to not exchange information with third parties about how they share data. Hereby the financial industry is not included in the research. While the interviews showed that workarounds took place, especially before specific privacy regulations to ease the way of sharing data. Systematic workarounds were not found in the interviews, possibly due to bias or the online setting.

Future studies should focus on action research in which data-sharing processes are being observed over a longer period of time, this could uncover deep-rooted workarounds which have become a blind spot for the organisation. This could also establish a more clear baseline from which the effect of these workarounds on the quantity of data being shared between organisations can be measured.

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APPENDIX - INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

The sections and information listed below were used to structure the interviews. It does not mean that this protocol represents all questions asked; rather, it was used as an initial framework only, which varied according to the participants and their willingness to share information.

Part 1: General information about the participants.

- Participant history at the organisation
- Job description
- Experience with sharing data with other organisations.

Part 2: Influence of privacy regulations on data sharing.

- Describe your tasks with regard to data sharing.
- Do you experience any hindrances from being compliant with privacy regulations?
- Have you ever decided not to share data out of fear of not being compliant?
- Is there a noticeable difference in the ease of sharing data before the enactment of stricter privacy regulations?

Part 3: Possible creation of workarounds

- In your experience, have information systems become harder to use since the stricter privacy regulations?
- In your experience, have you ever witnessed data being shared without following the correct procedures?
 - What was the reason for this deviation from the correct procedure?
 - Did this make it easier to accomplish the task?
- Did you see a difference in the number of unofficial processes being used since the enactment of stricter privacy regulations?